

BASELINE VARIABLES FOR CLIMATE MODEL INTERCOMPARISON AND EVALUATION

Community survey summary report

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List of acronyms

CMIP – Coupled Model Intercomparison Project

IPO – International Project Office

WCRP – World Climate Research Programme

WGCM – Working Group on Coupled Modelling

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1 Introduction

1.1 Context

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) has grown considerably and now serves a wide range of communities, all with their own specialised requirements for data. The CMIP Data Request function, led by Martin Jukes of UKRI-STFC and facilitated by the CMIP International Project Office (hereafter CMIP IPO) is establishing a process to address the challenges of too many variables listed as top priority, and its associated burden on the data providers, and the increasingly growing needs of CMIP data users. It is envisaged that a core set of variables can form a baseline for exchange of climate model data, in any intercomparison project, in accordance with FAIR data and Open Science principles. Establishing this baseline will address the community intention discussed at WGCM 2019 in Barcelona of giving more authority and meaning to variable prioritisation.

The intention is to publish the baseline variable set, together with an explanation of the process for modifying and extending this baseline set and a discussion on the role of the baseline variables in the context of the larger CMIP Data Request activity, as a Geoscientific Model Development (GMD) paper.

1.2 Development of the baseline variables: process and community co-creation

In spring 2022, members of the CMIP community were engaged in two phases of co-creation:

- **Phase 1:** An expression of interest survey was distributed by the CMIP IPO in April 2022 to those involved with CMIP6 and circulated by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP). 32 responses were received from respondents across Asia, Europe, and North America, whose CMIP6 involvement ranged from Data Request leads, modelling centre leads and MIP chairs, to users of CMIP data, for scientific and climate impact modelling as well as climate services provision. The findings from this survey were used to inform the development of Phase 2.
- **Phase 2:** Two workshops on the proposed methodological approach and a paper publication process to devise an agreed list of baseline variables were held during May 2022. A full description of the context, design, implementation and outcomes of the workshops and establishment of the paper author team can be found in the workshop report¹.

Following these first two phases of community engagement and co-creation, the newly established author team engaged in monthly meetings to ensure clarity around the purpose, function and intended (current and future) users of the identified baseline set of variables. Three meetings held between June and August 2022 were focused around the following activity areas:

- Development a skeleton structure of the paper.
- Determination and definition of audience/s for initial focus.
- Further sharing of use data to support baseline variable refinement.
- Development and approval of Phase 3 consultation format and content - a community survey.

¹ O'Rourke, E. and Turner, B. (eds). 2022: Priority variables for evaluation and exploitation of WCRP climate simulations workshop report Top priority variables community workshop - 12 and 17 May 2022. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.59555/TUOC4428>

This report will provide a summary of the Phase 3 community survey, an overview of the responses, and outline the next steps in the development of the baseline variables.

2 The community survey

2.1 Objective and format of the survey

The main objective of this Phase 3 community engagement survey was to gather further, and more detailed feedback and insight to guide the final development of the baseline variables paper. The survey was made up of four sections:

- **Part I:** Defining the context and structure of the baseline variable list.
- **Part II:** Feedback on specific variables (optional).
- **Part III:** Feedback on current and future process.
- **Part IV:** About the respondent.

Survey respondents were provided with a spreadsheet² containing details of the proposed baseline variables including the information and ranking methodology utilised to develop the identified list presented. To support a wider range of respondents' feedback on specific variables was optional. For those who chose to provide specific variable feedback a scoring table was provided to be provide consistency across reviews (see Table 1 below). The full survey form can be found in Annex A.

Table 1: To ensure review consistency a scoring definition against the three criteria was developed.

SCORE		DEFINITION
3	Excellent	The variable meets all requirements. Any shortcomings are minor.
2	Good	The variable fits the criterion well, but a number of significant shortcomings are present.
1	Poor	There are serious weaknesses.
0	Fail	The variable does not score on this criterion.
n/a	No opinion	No opinion on this variable/category for variable.

2.2 Target audience and distribution

The survey was targeted to a wider audience than the initial Phase 1 expression of interest survey with the scope broadened to include all those providing access to and/or utilising the outputs of climate models from across commercial, public and third sectors as well as academia. Discussion within the author team had highlighted the need to expand the definition of "data analysts" to beyond the climate

² <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>

science community to the many non-climate science and other users who are increasingly using climate data. To support understanding the roles in CMIP6 participation, guidance³ was utilised:

- Modellers produce the data (climate model data provider).
- Infrastructure providers enable access to the data (infrastructure service provider).
- Users consume the data (climate model data user).

The survey was open to respondents for a period of just over six weeks between 23rd August and 8th October 2022. The CMIP IPO ensured circulation across all CMIP and WCRP community lists and communication pathways including websites, social media channels and direct emails. In addition, the survey was distributed to organisations and platforms relevant to downstream users with the aim of encouraging feedback and contributions from those communities.

³ <https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/Guide/>

3 Overview of results

3.1 Profile of respondents

Overall, 44 responses were received with most respondents identifying as climate model data users (40) and 12 identified as climate model data providers with no responses from infrastructure service providers. It should be noted that respondents could select more than one category. In terms of career stage, there was a good balance of early (1-10 years), mid (11-25 years) and advanced (over 25 years) responses.

There was a strong bias in responses from Europe and North America with only one response from a country in the Global South. Science/academia responses also dominated with only nine responses from across commercial, government and public sector. These results exemplified the challenges the CMIP community has in engaging with these sectors and other downstream users. How this can be addressed will be an action for the CMIP IPO to work on going forward.

3.2 Utility and benefit of the baseline variable list

In Part I of the survey the respondents were asked to:

- Estimate the usefulness of the baseline variable list (using a scale of 1-5 with 1 representing no use and 5 representing extremely useful);
- Suggest how they thought the list would be used; and
- Suggest how the list could be improved (as a whole rather than based on individual variables).

There was a very strong positive response on the usefulness of the list with 80% giving a rating of 4 or 5. Model data providers emphasised the list would help them prioritise and provide those variables of most use to the wider community while meeting the need to maximise resource and energy efficiency. Data users responded that many of the variables useful for impacts and other downstream uses were included and greater consistency in availability of variables would support model intercomparison and multi-model evaluation. A small number of respondents (12) made suggestions on specific communities/sectors who would benefit particularly focused on the energy and renewables industry.

3.3 Specific variables feedback

There were 29 respondents who chose to review the shortlisted variables, with 12 of these reviewing more than five variables. They were asked to assess each variable against three criteria; clarity and precision, utility, and practicality; against the defined scoring table (see Table 1).

Of the 147 variables with proposed priority 1 in the spreadsheet⁴ provided with the survey, only 17 were suggested by respondents to Fail (0) or be Poor (1) against any of the criteria. Comments received from those reviewing included:

- There is a need for higher frequency variables e.g., hourly data needs from the renewable energy sector, and daily rather than monthly sea ice variables highlighted.
- Some confusion around pressure levels and ocean model grids.

⁴ <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>

- Variables relevant to overturning circulation analysis, greenhouse gas composition and calculation of water, energy and carbon budgets are missing.
- Request for additional surveying of user needs to identify new variable requirements.

3.4 Feedback on the current baseline variables process

There was an overall positive response for the current process to identify the baseline variables from the 50% of respondents who provided comment. However, some issues and comments to consider were raised including:

- Concern around the criteria used for prioritisation e.g., download volume may not be accurate given the use of data pools/archives at many centres for analysis, or that three-dimensional variables are given precedence due to larger volumes and file counts than two-dimensional fields.
- Variables that few models provide or are emerging needs may be excluded, with a heavy bias towards data streams produced in previous CMIP phases.
- Suggestion to include a size: value ratio to represent both the complexity and disk space occupied.
- The current process may be quite difficult for those outside the climate modelling community to understand and engage with, and therefore the downstream user communities are under-represented.

3.5 Feedback on maintenance and update of baseline variables

The baseline variables list is intended to be somewhat dynamic and responsive to emerging needs within the limitations of promoting consistency, managing the burden on the modelling centres and infrastructure providers, and the time required for robust expert review and consultation.

The respondents were asked how often the core variable list should be reviewed and updated given the options of annually, every two years, other, or no opinion. Every two years (16 respondents) and annually (13 respondents) were the most popular with those selecting "other" (8 respondents) largely indicating a view that the update should align with the relevant CMIP cycle/phase. The remaining respondents expressed no opinion. Suggestions on the process for maintenance and update included:

- The baseline variables list being available for ongoing review and comment.
- A platform for users to highlight missing or poorly populated variables to highlight future and emerging needs.
- Ensuring engagement with communities rather than individuals to avoid bias.
- Need to increase the diversity of engaged users e.g., potential engagement of UN Sustainable Development Goals experts to identify relevant additional required variables.

Respondents were also asked to suggest other activities and communities that could benefit and how the engagement process could be improved to ensure close engagement between the climate modelling and user communities. A small number of responses identified energy modellers and the energy industry together with other WCRP activities, the IPCC community, water management, and the wider impacts modelling community. In terms of methods to improve engagement there were a limited number of suggestions including collaboration with intermediary organisations, co-production approaches, and ensuring common understanding and expectation management between modelling centres and user communities.

4 Next steps

The author team have strongly welcomed the feedback, insight and suggestions provided by the survey respondents. They will now work to identify potential additional additions, confirmed inclusions and removals from the baseline variables list. A final technical meeting to review and finalise the list will take place during December 2022. Following this, the author team will work to finalise the final draft version of the paper and agree a timeline to submission during 2023. Community and user engagement will be encouraged during the GMD open review process with particular feedback from the wider WCRP community encouraged through open information events facilitated by the CMIP IPO.

Aligned to this effort will be the development of a strategic approach for the CMIP7 Data Request by the Data Request Task Team⁵ also led by Martin Juckes (UKRI-STFC) together with Chloe Mackallah (CSIRO).

⁵ For more information on the Data Request Task Team see <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7-task-teams/data-request/>

5 Annex A: Survey form

WCRP Priority Variables Consultation

Consultation response template

This form is a word document version of the online consultation form to aid answer preparation. All responses should be submitted using the form online by the closing date set out in the online form's introductory note. The online form is available at: <https://bit.ly/WCRP-CV-Phase2OnlineForm>

All answers are required unless indicated as optional.

Summary

Consultation on priority variables for inclusion within a core set of variables forming the baseline for exchange of climate model data, in any intercomparison project, in accordance with FAIR data and Open Science principles. Relevant to those involved in developing and operating climate models, data infrastructure and those utilising climate model outputs.

Respondents: those providing access to and/or utilising the outputs of climate models within commercial, public and third sectors as well as within academia.

This consultation is made up of 4 sections:

- Part I: Defining the context and structure of the core variable list,
- Part II: Feedback on specific variables (optional),
- Part III: Feedback on current and future process,
- Part IV: About the respondent.

You will be able to save a PDF of your submission.

Context

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) has grown considerably and now serves a wide range of communities, all with their own specialised requirements for data. The CMIP Data Request function, led by Martin Juckes of UKRI-STFC, is establishing a process to address the challenges presented by having too many variables listed as top priority while meeting the needs of both data providers and users.

It is envisaged that a core set of variables can form a baseline for exchange of climate model data, in any intercomparison project, in accordance with FAIR data and Open Science principles. Establishing this baseline will address the community intention discussed at WGCM 2019 in Barcelona of giving more authority and meaning to variable prioritisation.

The intention is to publish the core variable set, together with an explanation of the process for modifying and extending the core set and discussion of the role of the core variables in the context of the larger CMIP Data Request activity, as a Geoscientific Model Development (GMD) paper.

The core variable list will be based on the outcome of this consultation process. Starting from a list of over 1200 "priority 1" CMIP6 variables, a subset of 140 variables has been generated by an automated screening algorithm combining 4 criteria (1. Download volumes, 2. file counts, 3. Number of models supplying the data, 4. Inclusion in C3S service). This methodological approach is outlined here: <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>.

Contributors are not constrained by this list, they may propose that variables be removed, and others added, but the list is intended to provide some focus by giving an indication of the variables which are widely used according to the selected metrics. The expert consultation process is important to strike a compromise between competing metrics. We wish the final list to reflect a community view of priorities.

Consultation timetable:

- Consultation opens Tuesday 23 August.
- Consultation closes at **18.00 UTC on Friday 23 September**.
- CMIP IPO prepares a summary report for paper author team.

If you would like to work offline in preparing your answers, download a word doc version: <https://bit.ly/WCRP-CV-Phase2Form>

The work developing the core variables is being coordinated and led by Martin Juckes, UKRI-STFC. Its implementation is being supported by the CMIP International Project Office and is made possible by funding from IS-ENES3 part of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824084.

Data Protection

The following gives an overview of what happens to your personal information when you respond to this survey.

Your survey answers will be processed by the CMIP International Project Office. The data collected by the CMIP IPO will be stored for as long as necessary for the analysis of the survey and deleted after a period of 24 months at the latest.

Entries will only be shared with the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA), part of the Science and Technology Facilities Council, which is General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant. Aggregated data summaries will be shared with the author team.

If you have any requests, concerns, or questions regarding this notice, please contact: cmip-ipo@esa.int.

1. I confirm I have read and understood this data protection notice.

Answer options: YES

Part I: Defining the context and structure of the core variable list

For contextual information please review the 'Part I - Defining' tab on the Variable Prioritisation sheet <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology> which has further detail on:

- Form of the list
- Context in CMIP and other intercomparison projects
- Role from the modeller's perspective
- Role from the data analyst's perspective
- Role from the climate science and downstream user community perspective
- Role from the infrastructure provider and support perspective

The list of variables resulting from the methodological approach outlined in the "Methodology" tab is found in the "Variable prioritisation tab" . <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>

FORM OF THE LIST

The core variable list should also provide a model for clarity and interoperability.

- Each variable will have a clear definition, with descriptive metadata and mappings to GRIB and Essential Climate Variables.
- There will be some categorisation to support, for example, selective omission of high-volume variables.

CONTEXT IN CMIP AND OTHER INTERCOMPARISON PROJECTS

Intercomparison projects aiming at detailed analysis of climate processes and exploring new science will generally need a far greater range of variables than can be included in the core list. The core list provides a common baseline. The process for building a task specific list to address specific challenges is being addressed by the CMIP Task Team on Data in collaboration with the CMIP Panel (the Data TT is working on the process of compiling requests from multiple communities and a three-fold harmonisation process: harmonisation between communities, with modelling capacity, and with standards; the CMIP Panel, supported by the CMIP IPO, is working on the process of identifying the community representatives and setting an overall timeline for CMIP7).

ROLE FROM THE CLIMATE MODELLER'S PERSPECTIVE

A well-maintained baseline, with a clear and open mechanism for updates with a complete history of changes, provides software developers with certainty when new models and tools are being developed, and allows them to adapt to changes as they occur. All modelling groups are encouraged to maintain the ability to produce this core set and document where this is not possible.

ROLE FROM THE DATA ANALYST'S PERSPECTIVE

In the current archives any analyst that wishes to look at more than a few variables must make a choice between having heterogeneous diagnostics, with different sets of models for different variables, or limiting the number of models involved. Neither of these is ideal. By establishing a

clear and realistic baseline we hope to ensure that there is a greater level of consistency in the data collections, allowing more robust multi-variable analysis.

ROLE FROM THE CLIMATE SCIENCE AND DOWNSTREAM USER COMMUNITY PERSPECTIVE

The core variable list will contain a wide range of widely used variables, many of which are also present in other widely used parameter lists, such as the WMO GRIB codes and the GCOS Essential Climate Variables. The core list will provide a basis for mapping the relationships between these different ontologies and thus support free flow of information between the scientific communities associated with each family of standards and improved understanding for downstream users.

ROLE FROM THE INFRASTRUCTURE PROVIDER AND SUPPORT PERSPECTIVE

The existence of a stable core list will enable continuity in the development of infrastructure and software tools needed to support the expanding scope of WCRP MIP activities. Software developers outside the core infrastructure will be able to develop and maintain tools with confidence that there is a well-defined and predictable update cycle for the core variable list.

2. Indicate which of the 5 groups you identify with (you can select multiple if appropriate):
(Answer options: climate model data provider; infrastructure service provider; climate model data user – can select multiple)
3. Briefly explain your role/use of climate model data [optional]
(free text)
4. Please give your estimate of how useful the core list will be on a scale 1 (no use) to 5 (extremely useful)
[select number from 1–5]
5. If you would like to explain your estimate, please do so here [optional]
(free text)
6. Please say how you think the core list will be used
(free text)
7. Please say how the core list could be improved [optional]
(free text)

Part II: Feedback on Specific Variables

This section is optional.

We do not expect all contributors to review all variables. Please look at the list of variables found in the 'variable prioritisation' tab on the spreadsheet:

<https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>

Please identify a selection of variables which you will review, e.g., based on realm.

If 5 or less, fill out your answers in the text boxes below.

If more than 5 we suggest you use the Feedback template sheet as set out in steps 1–3 and for the questions below reference the tab number your response is entered onto.

- I. Duplicate the feedback template tab and assign it the next sequential number top left of the sheet.
- II. Rename the tab the assigned number.
- III. Mark sheet status top left as 'Scoring in progress'.
- IV. Complete the scoring for the variables you wish to focus on -highlight those you are scoring in yellow. Note, if you are going to start from the top and work down, please randomise the order first, so that we do not have a disproportionate number of reviews of the variables at the top of the list.
- V. Mark the sheet status as 'Submitted' and include the reference number when asked to below.

The scoring should be in the range of 0-3, as described in the table below.

The authors of this paper will seek to remedy any scores below 3 by either
 (a) correcting deficiencies in a variable definition or
 (b) removing the variable from the core variable list.

SCORE		DEFINITION
3	Excellent	The variable meets all requirements. Any shortcomings are minor.
2	Good	The variable fits the criterion well, but a number of significant shortcomings are present.
1	Poor	There are serious weaknesses.
0	Fail	The variable does not score on this criterion
na	No opinion	No opinion on this variable/category for variable

8. Are you happy to review variables shortlisted?
 - Yes (go to question 9)
 - No (go to question 13)
9. How many variables have you reviewed?
 - Five or less (see questions 8-9)
 - More than 5 (see question 10)
10. For each variable reviewed, name it and provide the score (na/0/1/2/3) for CP (Clarity & Precision), U(Utility) and P (Practicality) e.g., *Amon.va CP=3, U=2, P=1* [optional]
 If you have anything you'd like to share about your scoring, please do so here, clearing stating the variable and score you are referring to. [optional] (*free text*)
11. Please provide the google sheet tab reference number for your scoring [optional]

Part III: Feedback on current and future process

CURRENT PROCESS

The current process involved starting from a list of over 1200 "priority 1" CMIP6 variables, from which a subset of 140 variables has been generated by an automated screening algorithm combining four criteria:

- I. Download volumes.
- II. File counts.
- III. Number of models supplying the data.
- IV. Inclusion in C3S service.

This methodological approach is outlined here: <https://bit.ly/MIPVarMethodology>.

A publication summarising earlier community consultation, in the form of a survey and workshops, is available here: CMIP IPO Publication No.: 01/2022 <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-reports/#variables-workshop-report>

FUTURE UPDATES AND REVISIONS

The core variable list will be supplemented by MIP specific requests for CMIP7, but in the longer term, this list will also need to be updated and extended.

STAKEHOLDER LIST

The current stakeholder list is focused on CMIP and the CMIP6 endorsement process (using CMIP6 mailing lists).

12. CURRENT PROCESS –please comment on the current process of devising the core variable list [optional] (*free text*)
13. FUTURE UPDATES AND REVISIONS Frequency: how often should the core variable list be reviewed and updated? (*Answer options: Annually; Every 2 years; No opinion; (go to 15); Other*)
14. Do you have any other comments on future updates (e.g., methodology, governance) [optional] (*free text*)
15. STAKEHOLDER LIST: The current stakeholder list is focused on CMIP and the CMIP6 endorsement process. Can you identify other areas of WCRP activities that could benefit? [optional] (*free text*)
16. If the engagement process needs to be broader, how do we balance and facilitate the discussion between the modelling community and potential users? [optional] (*free text*)

Part IV: About the respondent

This consultation response is anonymous – we will not ask for your name or email address. We would however like to understand:

- Role and location of respondents
 - Equality Diversity and Inclusion- This section is optional. This information is collected by CMIP IPO to support an inclusive consultation process. Once summarised, we will use this aggregated information to inform next steps of the consultation, to further support diversity and inclusion.
17. ROLE & LOCATION Please let us know the country you are based in.
 18. ROLE & LOCATION Please let us know which category best reflects your current role:
 - Climate model data provider,
 - Infrastructure service provider,
 - Climate data user,
 - Other – please specify.

19. ROLE & LOCATION What sector(s) do you work in (multiple choice allowed)
- Science,
 - Commercial,
 - Third sector,
 - Government (national, regional, and local),
 - Public sector - non-policy making,
 - Other - please specify [optional].
20. EDI: Please select the option that matches your current career stage [optional]
- Early-career (0-10 years),
 - Mid-career (11-25 years),
 - Advanced-career (26+ years).
21. EDI Please let us know which gender you identify with. [optional]
[check box]
- Female,
 - Male,
 - Non-binary/non-conforming,
 - Prefer not to respond,
 - Prefer to self-describe [to question 26].
22. Which gender do you identify with: [optional]

Thank you!

Thank you for taking part in this survey. If you would like to receive a copy of the summary report, please request it by emailing CMIP-IPO@esa.int -this way your contact details are not linked with your response. If you would also like to be added to the CMIP IPO mailing list for notification of stakeholder engagement activities and community news, please include in your email "I'd like to be added to the CMIP IPO mailing list".

23. To help us improve our future consultation activities, please let us know how you heard about this consultation: [optional]
- CMIP IPO email,
 - WCRP website,
 - Social media,
 - Colleague,
 - Other -please specify (go to Q28).
24. Tell us how you heard about this consultation [optional] (*free text*)